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Science in context: An overview of all Wikipedia’s sources

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Abstract: Wikipedia stands on its sources: scientific articles and monographs, but also news media and online content. In fact, the number of news media and online content sources in Wikipedia is considerably larger than scientific ones. When considering Wikipedia as a source of altmetric data, this broader context of use becomes relevant. We provide a breakdown of Wikipedia sources by typology and an overview of how they are used in Wikipedia. We find that scientific sources are especially important in STEM Wikipedia, while news media sources find broader applicability. We also assess the reliability of news media sources in Wikipedia, finding that it is overall high. When news media sources are used in STEM Wikipedia, their selection for reliability is the strictest across Wikipedia.

Introduction

Wikipedia is a widely popular online encyclopedia (Singer et al. 2017; Smith 2020), making systematic use of primary and secondary sources via references (Piccardi et al. 2020). Given its reliance on scientific literature, Wikipedia qualifies as an altmetric source (Sugimoto et al., 2017; Babkina et al., 2021). The potential of Wikipedia as an altmetric source is still debated (Kousha & Thelwall, 2017), in part due to its radical openness and possible biases (Hube, 2017; Redi et al. 2019). Recently, Wikipedia sources have attracted more attention, with several studies providing increasingly more refined results (Arroyo-Machado et al. 2020; Zagovora et al. 2020; Singh et al., 2021). Scientific sources play a crucial yet specialized role in Wikipedia, in particular in support of scientific articles such as biology and medicine (Yang & Colavizza, 2022).

While the use of scientific sources in Wikipedia is being explored, our understanding of the relationship between these and other source typologies in Wikipedia remains limited (Lewoniewski et al., 2017; 2020). This is regrettable as the context of usage of a scientific source might not only influence its altmetric importance but also lead to a better understanding of the use of science in 'controversies' or otherwise contested knowledge areas. In this study, we expand upon our previous work (Yang & Colavizza, 2022) and offer an overview of all major source typologies in Wikipedia, looking at how scientific journal articles are used alongside books, news media, and other online sources. Furthermore, we provide a preliminary assessment of the reliability of news media sources in Wikipedia, in particular when used together with scientific

sources.

Data and methods

Our workflow proceeds as follows: firstly, we use the Wikipedia Citations open dataset to get all citations from Wikipedia to any source. Furthermore, we rely on Wikipedia Citation's own classification to distinguish between scientific sources, news media sources, and other source typologies. Next, we equip Wikipedia's articles with information on their contents. Lastly, we use an established service to gather information on the factual reliability of a news media source. The main datasets we use are further described in what follows.

Wikipedia Citations

Wikipedia Citations is the main dataset in this research (Singh et al., 2021). It consists of more than 29M citations extracted from the over 6M articles composing the English Wikipedia as of May 2020. In Wikipedia Citations, each citation is classified as given to a book, scientific journal article, news media source, or another source. In this dataset, 2.2M citations are given to journal articles, 3.2M books, 8.9M to news media, and 14.9M to other sources.

ORES topics and WikiProjects

For our analysis, following the approach of Yang & Colavizza (2022), we equip Wikipedia articles with information about their topics and WikiProjects they belong to, if any. The topics of Wikipedia articles are retrieved using the ORES Web service¹, which exposes a topic model of Wikipedia trained using Language-Agnostic Topic Classification (LATC)² (Johnson et al., 2021) and assigns each Wikipedia article to a taxonomy rooted in four categories: Geography, Culture, History and Society, and STEM. English Wikipedia currently includes over 2,000 WikiProjects, "A WikiProject is a group of contributors who want to work together as a team to improve Wikipedia"³. We add WikiProjects via a public dataset (Johnson and Halfaker, 2020).

Media Fact Check

In order to study the reliability of Wikipedia's news media sources, we extract data from the Media Bias Fact Check (MBFC)⁴, which contains a reliability rating for around 3600 media outlets. MBFC classifies news media sources into 9 categories, from high to low reliability, thus we extract data from each category and match it with our dataset via a source's domain name.

Results

In this study, we make use of all citations part of the Wikipedia Citations dataset. While journal articles make up for slightly over 7% of citations, news media sources play a larger role with about 30% of citations. In this and all subsequent analyses, we make use of fractional counting at the level of Wikipedia pages and their citations. For example, if a Wikipedia article belongs 60% to STEM and 40% to Culture, and cites 10 journal articles and 10 books, we will count them as 6 citations given to journal articles and to books from STEM, and 4 from Culture respectively. Counts are then normalized within topics; the same approach is followed for WikiProjects.

Our first result shows the breakdown of Wikipedia sources by typology, over macro-level ORES topics, in Table 1 and Figure 1. STEM Wikipedia articles make significantly higher use of journal

¹ <https://wiki-topic.toolforge.org/#lang-agnostic-model>

² <https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/ORES/ArticleTopic>

³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject>

⁴ <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com>

articles as sources, whilst articles belonging to History and Society, Geography, or Culture cite more books and news media sources. This trend is further confirmed when considering the top-10 WikiProjects (by the number of articles they contain). Medicine and the life sciences focus on journal articles, while humanities topics (e.g., Military history) make more use of books and country projects (e.g., Australia) in news media. The most important group of sources belonging to the 'Other' type are variations of the census and statistical data about countries.

Figure 1: Breakdown of source typology per Wikipedia ORES topic and main WikiProject.

Table 1: Breakdown of source typology per Wikipedia ORES topic.

Category	Journal_articles	Books	News_media	Other	Wikipedia articles
Overall	2,231,108 (7.6%)	3,231,330 (11%)	8,869,837 (30.3%)	14,944,392 (51.1%)	3,775,231 (100%)
STEM	1,291,250 (56%)	264,824 (12%)	215,323 (9%)	524,684 (23%)	207,608 (5.5%)
History_and_Society	157,264 (15%)	199,938 (19%)	306,943 (29%)	408,382 (37%)	38,894 (1%)
Geography	232,720 (12%)	375,651 (19%)	306,943 (27%)	840,537 (42%)	87,878 (2.3%)
Culture	224,714 (13%)	283,087 (17%)	482,331 (29%)	674,566 (41%)	69,390 (1.8%)
Other	325,160 (1%)	2,107,831 (9%)	7,323,900 (33%)	12,496,223 (57%)	3,371,461 (89.4%)

Using the Media Bias Fact Check database, we are able to assign a reliability score to 3,841,730 citations to news media sources, with a breakdown by typology as shown in Table 2. We remark how this is just a fraction of news media sources, and the coverage of Wikipedia articles by ORES topics is also limited.

Figure 2: The distribution of news media source reliability per Wikipedia ORES topics and top-10 WikiProjects.

Table 2: Breakdown of news media source reliability per Wikipedia ORES topic

Reliability	Generally reliable	No consensus	Generally unreliable	Wikipedia articles
Overall	2,683,039 (70%)	725,076 (19%)	433,615 (11%)	1,025,248 (100%)
STEM	357,275 (93%)	16,556 (4%)	10,599 (3%)	83,475 (8%)
History_and_Society	138,385 (74%)	38,236 (21%)	9,948 (5%)	19,583 (2%)
Geography	194,866 (71%)	59,376 (22%)	18,867 (7%)	34,274 (3%)
Culture	162,500 (72%)	46,903 (21%)	17,508 (7%)	31,595 (3%)
Other	1,830,013 (66%)	564,006 (20%)	376,693 (14%)	856,321 (84%)

Following a similar approach to Figure 1, we show the breakdown of news media source reliability by macro-level ORES topic and WikiProject, in Figure 2 and Table 2. Our results show that Wikipedia articles in general make use of reliable news media sources. Articles in STEM make the highest use of reliable sources, with YouTube as the main 'unreliable' one since this domain does not come with an editorial policy of sorts but it is a relatively open platform. The pattern is further confirmed by looking at WikiProjects, with certain ones making exclusive use of reliable news media sources (e.g., Molecular and cell biology).

Conclusions

We have studied the distribution of Wikipedia sources across broad typologies, qualifying usage by topics and WikiProjects. Taken together, our results show that Wikipedia makes a larger use of news media sources than scientific journal articles and books combined. What is more, news media sources cited in Wikipedia appear to be overall reliable, demonstrating the importance of establishing, consolidating, and following editorial guidelines in this respect.⁵ The use of sources in Wikipedia is localized and varies greatly according to the topic of an article. For example, STEM-related articles make much higher use of journal articles and are stricter in their use of news media sources too.

Looking at Wikipedia as an altmetric source, our results paint a more complex picture. On the one hand, the context of usage of a scientific source in Wikipedia could inform its altmetric importance by detecting scientific sources used alongside 'controversial' media sources. Looking at Wikipedia as an altmetric source, our results paint a more complex picture. On the one hand, the context of usage of a scientific source in Wikipedia could inform its altmetric

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Reliable_sources/Perennial_sources.

importance by detecting scientific sources used alongside 'controversial' media sources. On the other hand, scientific sources might become indirect Wikipedia sources via news media at a higher proportion and pace than we currently think (Fang & Costas, 2020). Our study has a set of limitations, including those coming from our data sources and a preliminary focus on coarse, top-level categories of analysis. We suggest that future work might profitably focus on lower, more granular levels of analysis, as well as on contested topics in Wikipedia, and their use of sources.

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